

Leveraging BIM for Public Works Execution and Accounting Optimization: BIM modelling and QTO for tender cost estimation

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Abstract

The construction industry, with its significant impact on the global economy, is undergoing a transformative shift through the adoption of Building Information Modelling (BIM). This thesis investigates into how BIM can optimize the execution and accounting of public works, focusing particularly on Quantity Take-Off (QTO) and cost estimation for tender processes. By leveraging automated workflows and advanced BIM technologies, the study seeks to improve the accuracy and efficiency of QTO practices, thus addressing the traditional challenges posed by manual methods.

Through a combination of comprehensive literature review, case studies, and empirical analysis, this research highlights the clear advantages of BIM-based QTO over conventional methods. Notable innovations in this thesis include the creation of quantification scripts that automatically calculate formwork quantities while accounting for overlaps and other complexities.

Another key development is a plugin that integrates a provincial price list into BIM software like Revit. Furthermore, the study utilises the IFC schema to inject information related to cost and task management, thereby enhancing interoperability and ensuring data consistency. The research also explores the use of IFC in Dynamo for computational tasks, showcasing the flexibility and potential of BIM technologies.

Implementing BIM for QTO and cost estimation in public works involves several best practices. These include utilizing standardized libraries and classification systems such as Uniformalt and Omniclass to ensure modeling consistency. Clearly defining the Level of Information Need (LOIN) for each project phase is crucial for maintaining detailed geometric and alphanumeric data. Incorporating parametric objects can enhance automation and streamline processes, while linking cost data directly with BIM elements allows for real-time cost computations and quantity take-offs. Custom property sets (Psets) are created to ensure consistent representation of relevant quantities. Additionally, implementing 4D BIM integrates scheduling information, and extending to 5D BIM combines 3D geometry with cost data, offering a comprehensive view of project development. Automated QTO processes using visual scripting tools like Dynamo minimize manual errors, and ensuring software interoperability with formats like IFC maintains consistency throughout the project lifecycle.

The findings reveal significant improvements in project management outcomes, such as reduced errors, better resource allocation, and streamlined processes. This study advocates for the widespread adoption of BIM, particularly the IFC4.x schema, for its enhanced information management capabilities. By integrating detailed cost and scheduling data directly into BIM models, better decision-making and project execution are facilitated, marking a substantial advancement in construction management.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/9PSFzBxSMPk>

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